

COVER SHEET FOR PROPOSAL TO THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION

PROGRAM ANNOUNCEMENT/SOLICITATION NO./CLOSING DATE/if not in response to a program announcement/solicitation enter NSF 04-2					FOR NSF USE ONLY	
FOR CONSIDERATION BY NSF ORGANIZATION UNIT(S) (Indicate the most specific unit known, i.e. program, division, etc.)					NSF PROPOSAL NUMBER	
OPP - ARCTIC RESRCH SUPPRT & LOGISTI					0425941	
DATE RECEIVED	NUMBER OF COPIES	DIVISION ASSIGNED	FUND CODE	DUNS# (Data Universal Numbering System)	FILE LOCATION	
				796268548		
EMPLOYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (EIN) OR TAXPAYER IDENTIFICATION NUMBER (TIN)		SHOW PREVIOUS AWARD NO. IF THIS IS <input type="checkbox"/> A RENEWAL <input type="checkbox"/> AN ACCOMPLISHMENT-BASED RENEWAL		IS THIS PROPOSAL BEING SUBMITTED TO ANOTHER FEDERAL AGENCY? YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> IF YES, LIST ACRONYM(S)		
		0101279				
NAME OF ORGANIZATION TO WHICH AWARD SHOULD BE MADE			ADDRESS OF AWARDEE ORGANIZATION, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.			
AWARDEE ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)			3535 College Road, Suite 101			
5300001191			Fairbanks, AK. 997093710			
NAME OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT FROM ABOVE			ADDRESS OF PERFORMING ORGANIZATION, IF DIFFERENT, INCLUDING 9 DIGIT ZIP CODE			
PERFORMING ORGANIZATION CODE (IF KNOWN)						
IS AWARDEE ORGANIZATION (Check All That Apply) (See GPG II.C For Definitions)		<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> FOR-PROFIT ORGANIZATION		<input type="checkbox"/> MINORITY BUSINESS <input type="checkbox"/> WOMAN-OWNED BUSINESS		<input type="checkbox"/> IF THIS IS A PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL THEN CHECK HERE
TITLE OF PROPOSED PROJECT Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program						
REQUESTED AMOUNT \$ 191,776	PROPOSED DURATION (1-60 MONTHS) 0 months		REQUESTED STARTING DATE		SHOW RELATED PRELIMINARY PROPOSAL NO. IF APPLICABLE	
CHECK APPROPRIATE BOX(ES) IF THIS PROPOSAL INCLUDES ANY OF THE ITEMS LISTED BELOW						
<input type="checkbox"/> BEGINNING INVESTIGATOR (GPG I.A)			<input type="checkbox"/> HUMAN SUBJECTS (GPG II.D.6)			
<input type="checkbox"/> DISCLOSURE OF LOBBYING ACTIVITIES (GPG II.C)			Exemption Subsection _____ or IRB App. Date _____			
<input type="checkbox"/> PROPRIETARY & PRIVILEGED INFORMATION (GPG I.B, II.C.1.d)			<input type="checkbox"/> INTERNATIONAL COOPERATIVE ACTIVITIES: COUNTRY/COUNTRIES INVOLVED (GPG II.C.2.j)			
<input type="checkbox"/> HISTORIC PLACES (GPG II.C.2.j)			_____			
<input type="checkbox"/> SMALL GRANT FOR EXPLOR. RESEARCH (SGER) (GPG II.D.1)			<input type="checkbox"/> HIGH RESOLUTION GRAPHICS/OTHER GRAPHICS WHERE EXACT COLOR REPRESENTATION IS REQUIRED FOR PROPER INTERPRETATION (GPG I.E.1)			
<input type="checkbox"/> VERTEBRATE ANIMALS (GPG II.D.5) IACUC App. Date _____						
PI/PD DEPARTMENT ARCUS		PI/PD POSTAL ADDRESS 3535 College Road, Suite 101				
PI/PD FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604		Fairbanks, AK 997093710				
		United States				
NAMES (TYPED)	High Degree	Yr of Degree	Telephone Number	Electronic Mail Address		
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick	HS	1973	907-474-1600	warnick@arcus.org		
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						
CO-PI/PD						

CERTIFICATION PAGE

Certification for Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant:

By signing and submitting this proposal, the individual applicant or the authorized official of the applicant institution is: (1) certifying that statements made herein are true and complete to the best of his/her knowledge; and (2) agreeing to accept the obligation to comply with NSF award terms and conditions if an award is made as a result of this application. Further, the applicant is hereby providing certifications regarding debarment and suspension, drug-free workplace, and lobbying activities (see below), as set forth in Grant Proposal Guide (GPG), NSF 04-2. Willful provision of false information in this application and its supporting documents or in reports required under an ensuing award is a criminal offense (U. S. Code, Title 18, Section 1001).

In addition, if the applicant institution employs more than fifty persons, the authorized official of the applicant institution is certifying that the institution has implemented a written and enforced conflict of interest policy that is consistent with the provisions of Grant Policy Manual Section 510; that to the best of his/her knowledge, all financial disclosures required by that conflict of interest policy have been made; and that all identified conflicts of interest will have been satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated prior to the institution's expenditure of any funds under the award, in accordance with the institution's conflict of interest policy. Conflicts which cannot be satisfactorily managed, reduced or eliminated must be disclosed to NSF.

Drug Free Work Place Certification

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Drug Free Work Place Certification contained in Appendix C of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Debarment and Suspension Certification

(If answer "yes", please provide explanation.)

Is the organization or its principals presently debarred, suspended, proposed for debarment, declared ineligible, or voluntarily excluded from covered transactions by any Federal department or agency?

Yes

No

By electronically signing the NSF Proposal Cover Sheet, the Authorized Organizational Representative or Individual Applicant is providing the Debarment and Suspension Certification contained in Appendix D of the Grant Proposal Guide.

Certification Regarding Lobbying

This certification is required for an award of a Federal contract, grant, or cooperative agreement exceeding \$100,000 and for an award of a Federal loan or a commitment providing for the United States to insure or guarantee a loan exceeding \$150,000.

Certification for Contracts, Grants, Loans and Cooperative Agreements

The undersigned certifies, to the best of his or her knowledge and belief, that:

(1) No federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid, by or on behalf of the undersigned, to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with the awarding of any federal contract, the making of any Federal grant, the making of any Federal loan, the entering into of any cooperative agreement, and the extension, continuation, renewal, amendment, or modification of any Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement.

(2) If any funds other than Federal appropriated funds have been paid or will be paid to any person for influencing or attempting to influence an officer or employee of any agency, a Member of Congress, an officer or employee of Congress, or an employee of a Member of Congress in connection with this Federal contract, grant, loan, or cooperative agreement, the undersigned shall complete and submit Standard Form-LLL, "Disclosure of Lobbying Activities," in accordance with its instructions.

(3) The undersigned shall require that the language of this certification be included in the award documents for all subawards at all tiers including subcontracts, subgrants, and contracts under grants, loans, and cooperative agreements and that all subrecipients shall certify and disclose accordingly.

This certification is a material representation of fact upon which reliance was placed when this transaction was made or entered into. Submission of this certification is a prerequisite for making or entering into this transaction imposed by section 1352, Title 31, U.S. Code. Any person who fails to file the required certification shall be subject to a civil penalty of not less than \$10,000 and not more than \$100,000 for each such failure.

AUTHORIZED ORGANIZATIONAL REPRESENTATIVE		SIGNATURE	DATE
NAME Wendy K Warnick		Electronic Signature	Feb 17 2004 7:49PM
TELEPHONE NUMBER 907-474-1600	ELECTRONIC MAIL ADDRESS warnick@arcus.org	FAX NUMBER 907-474-1604	

*SUBMISSION OF SOCIAL SECURITY NUMBERS IS VOLUNTARY AND WILL NOT AFFECT THE ORGANIZATION'S ELIGIBILITY FOR AN AWARD. HOWEVER, THEY ARE AN INTEGRAL PART OF THE INFORMATION SYSTEM AND ASSIST IN PROCESSING THE PROPOSAL. SSN SOLICITED UNDER NSF ACT OF 1950, AS AMENDED.

SUMMARY OF PROPOSED WORK

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$191,776 will support three new activities and will provide additional funding for three ongoing activities as part of the organizational support ARCUS provides to the U.S. Arctic science programs. These activities fall under the following major tasks identified in the cooperative agreement: 1) Arctic Community Science Planning; 2) NSF Arctic Sciences Section Coordination; and 3) Arctic Science Education. Several of the activities described here coordinate research-focused community workshops and meetings, one provides editorial and publication support or preparation and distribution of information to assist NSF and the arctic research community, and several expand education and outreach opportunities for undergraduate and graduate students and for teachers and researchers. All of the activities support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section or provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research.

The proposed activities that require supplemental funding are summarized below. Activities not previously included in this cooperative agreement are marked *New*. No new tasks are included. All activities fall under existing tasks and the scope of the cooperative agreement.

1. ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.3 Planning for Integrated Arctic Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

This supplemental funding will support the activities related to the development of an Arctic geographic information infrastructure, including two community planning meetings, an information-sharing web site, and follow-on community planning and development activities.

Accomplishments

- Worked with NSF to convene a North Slope GIS Meeting in Seattle, Washington in October 2003 in order to survey and discuss GIS efforts with respect to research and logistics support on the North Slope of Alaska. Worked with NSF and meeting organizer, Allison Graves of Nuna Technologies, to arrange meeting logistics, technical requirements and prepare participant materials for the meeting. Staffed the 20-person meeting.
- Worked with NSF to convene an Arctic GIS Planning meeting in Seattle, Washington in November 2003 in order discuss important next steps in implementing improvements to Arctic Geospatial Information Infrastructure (Arctic GII). Worked with NSF to arrange meeting logistics, technical requirements, and prepare participant materials. Staffed the 31-person meeting.
- Worked with NSF to develop an Arctic GIS Website in order to reflect recent developments in Arctic GII and to provide the arctic GIS community with information and services to facilitate development of a coordinated Arctic GII. The website includes:
 1. Introduction and background information on Arctic GIS and GII themes and developments
 2. Information and summaries of NSF-sponsored Arctic GIS meetings
 3. Several pages of annotated weblinks relevant to Arctic GII
 4. News and Events page

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5. Discussion Forum – an on-line bulletin board to foster discussion and collaboration within the community of GIS professionals, arctic scientists, resource managers, data providers and the wider community on issues related to Arctic Geospatial Information Infrastructure (AGII). The Forum includes open-ended user-defined discussion threads, as well as providing an avenue for moderated thematic discussions.
- Sent draft Arctic GIS Website to various Arctic GIS researchers and professionals for comment and input January 2004.
 - Published Arctic GIS Website February 2004 and engaged in significant outreach activities in order to inform and engage researchers and GIS professionals regarding website development; published announcements via ArcticInfo and ARCUS website.
 - Hosted a teleconference January 2004 to survey and coordinate plans for proposed Arctic GIS projects in support of logistics; worked with teleconference organizer Allison Graves to coordinate technical, logistic, and content issues of the teleconference.

Projected Activities

Continued development of Arctic GIS Website and Online Discussion Forum:

- Add content and products to the website as determined by NSF and arctic GIS community.
- Further develop the Online Discussion Forum for targeted thematic discussions to advance GII efforts; work with NSF and the GIS community to select forum topics and moderators.

1.4.1 Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Open Science Meeting (OSM)

This supplemental funding will support the additional costs of the SEARCH Open Science Meeting (OSM), held in October 2003. The SEARCH OSM was originally planned for 300 participants. As participants continued to register, the decision was made by the SEARCH Steering Committee to accommodate as many participants as possible. Over 440 people participated in the meeting, which increased the overall meeting support costs. Information about the overall accomplishments is included here to provide an understanding of the scale of the meeting and the complexities of meeting support and facilitation.

Accomplishments

- Worked with 10-person Organizing Committee (OC) to develop program focus and structure of the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH) Open Science Meeting (OSM) to provide an international forum to present and discuss research on arctic environmental changes occurring across terrestrial, oceanic, atmospheric, and human systems.
- Worked with SEARCH OSM OC to formulate a draft agenda, which was circulated to the SEARCH Science Steering Committee, representatives from the Interagency Working Group (IWG), and the International Arctic SC (IASC) for comment and input April and May 2003. The agenda included a combination of invited keynote talks, panel discussions, parallel science sessions with contributed talks, and poster sessions. Major themes around which the agenda was organized were:
 1. Day 1: Changes and Impacts; Day 1 Parallel Science Sessions included “Changes on Land,” “Changes in the Sea,” “Changes in the Atmosphere,” and “Coastal Processes”
 2. Day 2: Feedbacks; Day 2 Parallel Science Sessions included “Social Feedbacks,” “Biological Feedbacks,” and “Physical Feedbacks”
 3. Day 3: Drivers and Causes
 4. Day 4: International Implementation

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- Distributed conference announcements via ArcticInfo, ARCUS website, and via hardcopy at various conferences and meetings, including a call for input and suggestions, calls for presentation and poster abstracts, and registration and logistics announcements.
 - Created a SEARCH OSM poster for outreach purposes; presented poster at the American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) Arctic Science Conference meeting in Fairbanks, Alaska.
 - Recruited and invited speakers, panelists, and science session co-chairs; the invited contributors included 21 keynote speakers, 13 panelists and 16 co-chairs from a variety of universities, research institutes, government agencies, and indigenous organizations.
 - Facilitated the development of the parallel science sessions by working with the OSM OC and the 16 science session co-chairs to compile submitted abstracts and guide the abstract selection process.
 - Convened a science session co-chair teleconference and worked with the co-chairs to recruit speakers and develop final parallel science session agendas, which included 76 contributed talks on a wide range of geographic, disciplinary, and thematic foci.
 - Worked with over two-dozen arctic researchers, conference center staff and hotels to coordinate the planning of 23 associated meetings that were held in conjunction with the SEARCH OSM. These side meetings represented a variety of topical, organizational, and disciplinary foci, and ranged from small groups holding working meetings on an arctic science issue to larger town meetings held to gather input on international programs.
 - Developed a SEARCH Open Science Meeting website and prepared and maintained content including agenda, registration, abstract, side meeting and general logistics information.
 - Developed and tracked on-line registration process and added capability to accept credit card payments.
 - Developed, edited, and maintained online searchable database of submitted oral and poster abstracts.
 - Worked with NSF publications office and other arctic organizations and programs to gather outreach and informational materials for display at the conference.
 - Worked with the OSM Organizing Committee, and media liaisons from NSF, University of Washington, and NASA to engage print, radio, and Internet media and to arrange a press event held at the conference; significant press interest and several stories resulted.
 - Arranged and paid for travel and accommodations for keynote speakers and other key participants, including select student scholarship recipients.
 - Prepared final meeting materials including agenda, venue and travel information, participant list, preliminary abstracts; provided information via website and participant notebooks with CD-ROM.
 - Coordinated all logistic and technical requirements for the conference with conference center and hotels; worked with the telecommunications company Vision Net, Inc., to provide press event and plenary sessions to public via streaming video.
 - Managed the conference activities and provided staff support for the 4-day conference of 454 participants and 23 associated side meetings. Participants represented 177 organizations from 18 countries equaling 19% international participation.
 - Developed and published on website post-meeting materials and information, including final agenda, abstracts, powerpoint presentations, participant list, compilation of media coverage, and edited video streaming.

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- Worked with science session co-chairs and Organizing Committee to prepare the final conference proceedings, including an introductory executive summary, summary of the parallel science sessions, full abstracts, and participant list.

1.4.2 *New* Support Student Participation in the SEARCH Open Science Meeting (OSM)

ARCUS was asked by the SEARCH OSM organizing committee to develop a student scholarship program to ensure the rigorous and productive participation of young investigators in the SEARCH OSM.

Accomplishments

- Developed and administered merit-based student scholarship program to encourage the participation of young investigators; funded some portion of participation costs for 38 undergraduate and graduate students representing 21 institutions and 5 countries; students represented a diverse array of over one dozen scientific disciplines, including anthropology, biology, ecology, economics, hydrology, geography, geophysics, and natural resource management.
- Managed student poster contest, including the development of judging criteria, selection of judges, and presentation of poster contest results at the conference. ARCUS partnered with the Arctic Institute of North America (AINA) to offer awards to the three competition winners. The winners will receive support to attend a relevant conference on the Arctic and their work will be highlighted at the 2004 Arctic Forum in Washington DC. They also will receive a two-year Arctic Institute of North America membership, which includes a subscription to the interdisciplinary journal ARCTIC.
- ARCUS also worked with the Alaska Native Science Commission (ANSC) to insure representation and participation of Alaska Native students; 5 Alaskan Native students were sponsored.

1.8 *New* Community Survey to Identify Arctic Research Data Coordination and Data Management Needs

A clear need has emerged through a number of Arctic planning activities, conferences and meetings for better information about needs and problems in data coordination and data management for Arctic research in general and specifically for projects and programs that are inter-disciplinary, multi-institutional, international in scope, or interagency. ARCUS proposed to conduct a community survey using the online survey system that we have developed. The survey will be launched in late March and continue for several months. Planning of the survey tool has been initiated and the formation of a small advisory group is in planning.

2. NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION

2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials

At the request of the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, ARCUS produced an information and outreach poster, Arctic Science Discoveries, which described Arctic Sciences Sections activities and programs. ARCUS has provided a number of large format, laminated copies of the poster to NSF, as well as small format glossy versions for outreach purposes.

3. ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION

3.1 *New* Teachers and Researchers – Exploring and Collaborating

The Teachers & Researchers - Exploring and Collaborating (TREC) program is an educational research experience in which K-12 teachers participate in Arctic research, working closely with scientists, as a pathway to improving science education through teachers' experiences in scientific inquiry. The participating TREC teachers serve as a conduit for reciprocal exchange of experience and knowledge between researchers and educators, and as a foundation for a growing community of students, educators, researchers and the general public that is engaged in science teaching and learning. TREC is a collaborative network of teachers, researchers, students, and community members. Through TREC, teachers will have the opportunity to increase their knowledge, enhance teaching skills, transfer their experiences to the classroom, engage in leadership roles, and develop a supportive network of researchers and education colleagues.

Supplemental funding will support the initial planning and launch of the TREC program, the development of a TREC web site, and the application and selection and matching process for teachers and researchers. Additional activities will be continued into the next cooperative agreement year. Accomplishments thus far are listed below.

Accomplishments

- Worked with NSF to convene management group in partnership with VECO Polar Resources.
- Worked with management group to determine scope of program, program planning components, and task scheduling.
- Developed program materials, including program description and participation requirements for teachers and researchers; announced program via Arctic Info, ARCUS website, and education listservs.
- Developed and launched TREC website, which includes program information, participation requirements, online application process, weblinks, and structure for program participants to interact online.
- Designed and implemented application process for teachers and researchers.
- Convened selection committee to select teachers and researchers from applicant pool.
- Convened advisory committee to assist in program, content, and curriculum development.
- Selected and matched teachers and researchers to participate in field experience for Summer 2004.
- Selected and developed tools to facilitate the online collaboration between teachers, researchers, and the community, including webinars (real-time seminars broadcast over the Internet), bulletin board forums, chat capabilities, file sharing workspace, on-line calendar and field journals.
- Developed content for the orientation webinars.
- Conducted four (4) orientation webinars for participating teachers and researchers.

SUMMARY

ARCUS has facilitated scientific planning for arctic research efforts for over ten years by working with the scientific community through surveys, workshops, Internet communications, and other means to define science priorities and research initiatives. ARCUS has organized dozens of workshops and published numerous scientific planning documents, which reflect the recommendations of the arctic research community on scientific priorities in various research fields. All of the activities described in this request for supplemental funds support the community science planning process for the NSF Arctic Sciences Section and provide information and support for the conduct of Arctic research and, therefore, will contribute to the overall excellence and advancement of arctic research supported by the National Science Foundation.

JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SUPPLEMENT

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$191,776 to the funding already awarded through No. OPP-0101279 is necessary because:

1. Three activities described in this request, Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC), supporting students to participate in the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, and a community survey on data coordination and management needs are new activities.
2. One activity, the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, was originally budgeted at a level much lower than actually took place, which increased the overall meeting support costs.
3. One activity, GIS Planning, is not a new activity but no activities were included in the original budget for the current program year. At NSF's request, ARCUS hosted two meetings in October 2003 and supported the development of an information coordination web site for Arctic GIS and GIL.
4. Arctic Section Science Materials is not a new activity but no project activities were included in the initial budget for the current program year. At NSF's request, ARCUS produced an information and outreach poster described in this request.

All of the activities described here are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF), providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to undertake these new or additional activities at the request of and on behalf of NSF and the arctic research community, the SEARCH Interagency Working Group and SEARCH Open Science Meeting organizing committee, and other participants in and managers of aspects of arctic research. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF Program Managers as well.

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET YEAR 1

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
	CAL	ACAD	SUMR				
1. Wendy K Warnick - none	0.00	0.00	0.00	\$	0	\$	
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. (0) OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES	0.00	0.00	0.00		0		
2. (5) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)	5.55	0.00	0.00		20,313		
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS					0		
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS					4,017		
5. (1) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)					380		
6. (0) OTHER					0		
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)					24,710		
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)					8,479		
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)					33,189		
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT					0		
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)					-2,157		
2. FOREIGN					0		
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____					0		
2. TRAVEL _____					-4,339		
3. SUBSISTENCE _____					20,713		
4. OTHER _____					0		
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS					16,374		
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES					12,877		
2. PUBLICATION COSTS/DOCUMENTATION/DISSEMINATION					-6,919		
3. CONSULTANT SERVICES					15,228		
4. COMPUTER SERVICES					4,037		
5. SUBAWARDS					0		
6. OTHER					61,480		
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS					86,703		
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)					134,109		
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE) Indirect on Total Direct - Subcontracts (Rate: 43.0000, Base: 134109)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)					57,667		
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)					191,776		
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)					0		
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)				\$	191,776	\$	
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0 AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$							
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
		Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG			

SUMMARY PROPOSAL BUDGET Cumulative

ORGANIZATION Arctic Research Consortium of the U.S.				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
				PROPOSAL NO.	DURATION (months)		
PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR / PROJECT DIRECTOR Wendy K Warnick				AWARD NO.	Proposed	Granted	
A. SENIOR PERSONNEL: PI/PD, Co-PI's, Faculty and Other Senior Associates (List each separately with title, A.7. show number in brackets)				NSF Funded Person-months		Funds Requested By proposer	Funds granted by NSF (if different)
				CAL	ACAD	SUMR	
1. Wendy K Warnick - none				0.00	0.00	0.00	\$ 0 \$
2.							
3.							
4.							
5.							
6. () OTHERS (LIST INDIVIDUALLY ON BUDGET JUSTIFICATION PAGE)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
7. (1) TOTAL SENIOR PERSONNEL (1 - 6)				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
B. OTHER PERSONNEL (SHOW NUMBERS IN BRACKETS)							
1. (0) POST DOCTORAL ASSOCIATES				0.00	0.00	0.00	0
2. (5) OTHER PROFESSIONALS (TECHNICIAN, PROGRAMMER, ETC.)				5.55	0.00	0.00	20,313
3. (0) GRADUATE STUDENTS							0
4. (1) UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS							4,017
5. (1) SECRETARIAL - CLERICAL (IF CHARGED DIRECTLY)							380
6. (0) OTHER							0
TOTAL SALARIES AND WAGES (A + B)							24,710
C. FRINGE BENEFITS (IF CHARGED AS DIRECT COSTS)							8,479
TOTAL SALARIES, WAGES AND FRINGE BENEFITS (A + B + C)							33,189
D. EQUIPMENT (LIST ITEM AND DOLLAR AMOUNT FOR EACH ITEM EXCEEDING \$5,000.)							
TOTAL EQUIPMENT							0
E. TRAVEL 1. DOMESTIC (INCL. CANADA, MEXICO AND U.S. POSSESSIONS)							-2,157
2. FOREIGN							0
F. PARTICIPANT SUPPORT COSTS							
1. STIPENDS \$ _____ 0							
2. TRAVEL _____ -4,339							
3. SUBSISTENCE _____ 20,713							
4. OTHER _____ 0							
TOTAL NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS (0) TOTAL PARTICIPANT COSTS							16,374
G. OTHER DIRECT COSTS							
1. MATERIALS AND SUPPLIES							12,877
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5. SUBAWARDS							0
6. OTHER							61,480
TOTAL OTHER DIRECT COSTS							86,703
H. TOTAL DIRECT COSTS (A THROUGH G)							134,109
I. INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)(SPECIFY RATE AND BASE)							
TOTAL INDIRECT COSTS (F&A)							57,667
J. TOTAL DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS (H + I)							191,776
K. RESIDUAL FUNDS (IF FOR FURTHER SUPPORT OF CURRENT PROJECTS SEE GPG II.C.6.j.)							0
L. AMOUNT OF THIS REQUEST (J) OR (J MINUS K)							\$ 191,776 \$
M. COST SHARING PROPOSED LEVEL \$ 0				AGREED LEVEL IF DIFFERENT \$			
PI/PD NAME Wendy K Warnick				FOR NSF USE ONLY			
ORG. REP. NAME* Wendy Warnick				INDIRECT COST RATE VERIFICATION			
				Date Checked	Date Of Rate Sheet	Initials - ORG	

C *ELECTRONIC SIGNATURES REQUIRED FOR REVISED BUDGET

**Arctic Research Consortium of the United States, Inc.
Request for Supplemental Funding Year 3, Award OPP-0101279**

1 ARCTIC COMMUNITY SCIENCE PLANNING

1.3 GIS Planning

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	3,197
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	
Participant Support Costs	1,633
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	1,744
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	5,279
Total direct costs	11,853
Indirect Costs	5,097
TOTAL COSTS	16,950

1.4.1 SEARCH Open Science Meeting

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	12,815
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	(2,157)
Participant Support Costs	(13,204)
Materials and Supplies	9,877
Publications/Dissemination	(9,537)
Consulting	7,228
Computer Services	287
Subcontracts	
Other Direct Costs	48,370
Total direct costs	53,679
Indirect Costs	23,082
TOTAL COSTS	76,761

1.4.2 SEARCH OSM Student Support (NEW)

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	27,945
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	831
Total direct costs	28,776
Indirect Costs	12,374
TOTAL COSTS	41,150

1.8 Data Coordination (NEW)

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	-
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	5,000
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	5,000
Indirect Costs	2,150
TOTAL COSTS	7,150

2 NSF ARCTIC SCIENCES SECTION COORDINATION**2.1 Arctic Section Science Materials**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	210
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and Supplies	-
Publications/Dissemination	874
Consulting	-
Computer Services	-
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	-
Total direct costs	1,084
Indirect Costs	466
TOTAL COSTS	1,550

3 ARCTIC SCIENCE EDUCATION**3.5 TREC (NEW)**

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	16,967
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel (domestic/foreign)	-
Participant Support Costs	-
Materials and supplies	3,000
Publications/Dissemination	-
Consulting	3,000
Computer Services	3,750
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	7,000
Total direct costs	33,717
Indirect Costs	14,499
TOTAL COSTS	48,216

TOTAL

Salaries and Fringe Benefits	33,189
Permanent Equipment	-
Travel	(2,157)
Participant Support Costs	16,374
Materials and Supplies	12,877
Publications/Dissemination	(6,919)
Consulting	15,228
Computer Services	4,037
Subcontracts	-
Other Direct Costs	<u>61,480</u>
Total direct costs	134,109
Indirect Costs @ 43%	57,667
Total direct and indirect	<u><u>191,776</u></u>

Budget Justification – Supplement Request

This is a request for a supplement to ARCUS' cooperative agreement with the National Science Foundation (No. OPP-0101279). The supplement of \$191,776 to the funding already awarded is necessary because of the following activities that ARCUS has been asked to take on in addition to those activities budgeted in the award.

1. Three activities, Teachers and Researchers Exploring and Collaborating (TREC), supporting students to participate in the SEARCH Open Science Meeting, including some portion of participation costs for 38 undergraduate and graduate students, and a community survey on data coordination and management needs are new activities.
2. One activity, the SEARCH Open Science Meeting was originally budgeted at a level of 300 participants. As participants continued to register, the decision was made by the SEARCH Steering Committee to accommodate as many participants as possible. Over 440 people participated in the meeting, which increased the overall meeting support costs.
3. GIS Planning is not a new activity but no activities were included in the budget in the current program year. At NSF's request, ARCUS hosted an Arctic GIS Planning meeting and a North Slope GIS meeting in October 2003, following the SEARCH Open Science Meeting and supported the development of an information coordination web site for Arctic GIS and GII.
4. Arctic Section Science Materials is not a new activity but no project activities were included in the initial budget in the current program year. At the request of the NSF Arctic Sciences Section, ARCUS produced an information and outreach poster, Arctic Science Discoveries, which described Arctic Sciences Sections activities and programs.

All of the activities described here are in keeping with and part of ARCUS' work for the National Science Foundation (NSF), providing organizational support for the U.S. arctic science programs.

ARCUS is submitting this supplement request to undertake these new or additional activities at the request of and on behalf of NSF and the arctic research community, the SEARCH Interagency Working Group and SEARCH Open Science Meeting organizing committee, and other participants in and managers of aspects of arctic research. The specific activities and the support that will be provided have been discussed with the relevant NSF Program Managers as well.

Item A: Senior Personnel

No additional resources are requested for Senior Personnel

Item B: Other Personnel

Resources are being requested for a total of 5.5 person months for senior personnel salaries and benefits required to develop, coordinate and manage the activities described above. ARCUS has employed an undergraduate student to produce and edit videos of the

presentations from the SEARCH Open Science Meeting. Additional clerical labor was also required to support travel arrangements for the additional student participants at the workshop.

Item C: Fringe Benefits

ARCUS charges actual fringe benefits costs on direct salaries. The fringe rate for budgeting purpose is 35%.

Items E and F: Travel and Participant Support

Additional resources are being requested to partially support the attendance of 4 GIS experts at the GIS meetings held in conjunction with the SEARCH Open Science Meeting and of the 30 students awarded scholarships to attend SEARCH. These costs are offset in part by savings on both staff and participant travel to the meeting

Item G: Other Direct Costs

Line 1. Materials and Supplies

Resources are requested to support the incremental cost of supplying the additional participants and student participants at the SEARCH meeting as well as the cost to supply TREC teachers with digital cameras and supplies needed to go to the field.

Line 2. Publication/Documentation and Dissemination

The cost of reprinting the GIS report and printing the Arctic Section poster was offset by budgeted printing costs for the SEARCH proceedings, which will not take place in the current program year. These savings help to reduce the overall supplement request.

Line 3. Consultant Services

A consultant is doing additional programming for the survey instrument for the data coordination survey activity. A web designer developed the web page design and templates for TREC. Video streaming services for the three-day SEARCH meeting were supplied at no cost to ARCUS. Resources are requested for editing the archived video stream from the Search Open Science Meeting, however.

Line 4. Computer Services

To facilitate and support webinars and communications amongst TREC participants, ARCUS will enter into a channel license agreement with Horizon Live, a company that provides cross-platform software to support live Web-based teaching and communication.

Line 6. Other

Resources are requested to cover the cost of conference meeting support for the additional participants at the GIS and SEARCH meetings. \$10,000 received from Sandia National Laboratories in support of student participation in the conference has been applied to reduce the total request. The TREC program will also cover the cost of temporary labor charges to pay for substitute teachers for TREC teacher participants.